

method of determining 'a' from viscosity measurements, since, 'S' can be calculated from theory. Furthermore, at $C=C_0$, $(C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3})=0$ and hence $B = (\eta_r - 1)/C_0$ and as inter-ionic attraction disappears at C_0 , B should be an additive property of the ions as observed by Cox and Wolfenden¹⁰.

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Synthesis and Cardiovascular Activity of Substituted-4-Azetidinones†

A. KUMAR, S. GURTU, J. C. AGARWAL,
J. N. SINHA, K. P. BHARGAVA
and K. SHANKER*

Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics,
King George's Medical College,
Lucknow-226 003

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THE cyclo addition of chloroacetyl chloride and thioglycolic acid in different anils on azomethine group, $-CH=N-$, such as thenylidene¹, *p*-(2'-thianlylidene amino) acetophenone¹ yields azetidines and thiazolidinones.

The azetidines of 2-acetylphenothiazine have not been synthesized so far. Moreover, the phenothiazine nucleus possesses potent biological activities²⁻⁵ including cardiovascular activity⁶. 2-Acetyl-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazine (III) was condensed with substituted aromatic aldehydes to yield arylidene-2-acetyl-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazine (IVa-1) by refluxing in dry toluene in the presence of glacial acetic acid⁷.

The cycloaddition reaction of monochloroacetyl chloride on azomethine group ($-CH=N-$) in (IVa-1) yielded the corresponding substituted-4-azetidines (Va-1). Compounds thus synthesized are given in Table 1.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer, Model 137 spectrophotometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}). NMR spectra were recorded on Varian 90D instrument using TMS as internal standard. TLC was done on silica gel G.

2-Acetyl phenothiazine (I) and 2-acetyl-10-(chloroacetyl) phenothiazine (II) were prepared by known methods.

2-Acetyl-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazine (III): A mixture of 2-acetyl-10-(chloroacetyl) phenothiazine (0.03 mole) in absolute ethanol and hydrazine hydrate (99%) (0.45 mole) was refluxed for 20 hr, solvent was removed and the solid mass that separated out was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 215-216°, yield 80%. (Found: N, 13.01. $C_{16}H_{18}N_3O_2S$ requires N, 13.42%). IR of III showed characteristic bands at 3420 ($-NH$) and 1690 ($-C=O$) cm^{-1} .

Arylidene-2-acetyl-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazines (IVa-1): To a solution of 2-acetyl-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazine (III) (0.01 mole) in toluene (dry, 50 ml) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid was added the respective substituted benzaldehyde (0.01 mole) and the mixture refluxed for 10 to 12 hr.

Scheme

† Part of the work will be incorporated in the Ph.D. thesis of A.K.

* For correspondence.

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (IVa-1)

Compd. No.	R	m.p. °C	Recrystallization solvent	Yield %	Molecular formula	Cardiovascular activity			ALD ₅₀ mg/kg i.p.
						Dose I.V. (mg/kg)	Change in B.P. (mm of Hg)	Effect on CO and NE	
IVa	2-Cl	78	Ethanol	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	5	No effect	No effect	> 1000
IVb	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	154	DMF/water	55	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	5	-80	No effect	> 1000
IVc	4-OH	195	Ethanol/water	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	5	No effect	No effect	> 1000
IVd	4-OCH ₃	104	"	50	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	5	-60	No effect	> 1000
IVe	3,4-Cl	247	"	65	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ SCl ₂	5	-40	NE response partially inhibited	> 1000
IVf	2-OH, 4-OCH ₃	236-37	Benzene/Pet. ether	50	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂ S	5	-30	NE response partially inhibited	> 1000
IVg	4-NO ₂	150-52	Ethanol/water	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	10	-50	-No effect	> 1000
IVh	3-CH ₃	142	"	75	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	5	-80	No effect	> 1000
IVi	4-COOC ₂ H ₅	64	"	70	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄ S	5	-80	-NE response	> 1000
IVj	4-OOCH ₃	118	"	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	5	No effect	No effect	> 1000
IVk	3-OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₅	207	DMF/water	65	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₄ S	5	No effect	No effect	> 1000
IVl	3,4,5-OCH ₃	225	"	75	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	5	No effect	No effect	> 1000

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (Va-1)*

Compd. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Cardiovascular activity			ALD ₅₀ mg/kg i.p.
					Dose I.V. mg/kg	Change in B.P.** (mm of Hg)	Effect on CO and NE	
Va	2-Cl	105	45	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ S	1	-10 and then +10	No effect	> 500
Vb	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	122	50	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	1	No effect	No effect	> 500
Vc	4-OH	185	60	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	1	No effect	No effect	> 500
Vd	4-OCH ₃	124	40	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	1	-20 and then +20	"	> 500
Ve	3,4-Cl	158	55	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ S	1	No effect	"	> 500
Vf	2-OH, 4-OCH ₃	174	60	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	1	No effect	"	-
Vg	4-NO ₂	252	50	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ ClS	1	No effect	"	-
Vh	3-CH ₃	186	40	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	1	-10	"	-
Vi	4-OOCC ₆ H ₅	262	45	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	1	-10	"	-
Vj	4-OOCH ₃	154	50	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	1	No effect	"	-
Vk	4-OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₅	134	55	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	1	No effect	"	-
Vl	3,4,5-OCH ₃	274	45	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	1	No effect	"	-

* Elemental analyses for compounds were within ±0.4% of theoretical value.

** - Indicates decrease and + indicates increase.

The solvent was distilled off to yield a residue which was washed with petroleum ether (40-60°) and recrystallized from appropriate solvent (Table 1). IR of IVh showed a band at 1640 cm⁻¹ characteristic of C=N stretching. NMR (IVh) (TFA): δ 6.7-8.0 (m, 11 H, ArH); 2.55 (s, 2H, -N-CO-CH₂-); 2.8 (s, 1H, NH); 8.4 (s, 1H, -N=CH-); 2.05 (s, 3H, CH₃-Ar); 2.35 (s, 3H, -COCH₃-Ar) (ppm).

Substituted-4-azetidiones (Va-1): To a stirred solution of IV (0.01 mole) and triethylamine (0.02 mole) in dioxane (dry, 50 ml) was added monochloroacetyl chloride (0.02 mole) dropwise at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min and then refluxed for 3 hr. A solid was obtained on removal of dioxane, which was recrystallized from a mixture of ethanol/water (Table 2). IR of Vh showed band at 1740 (C=O, monocyclic/β-lactam), with additional band at 1720 (C=O) cm⁻¹. NMR (Vh) (CDCl₃): δ 6.7-8.0 (m, 11H, ArH); 2.5 (s, 2H, -N-CO-CH₂-); 4.45 (s, 1H, NH); 4.0 (d, 1H, J=9Hz, -N-CH-), 6.4 (d, 1H, J=9Hz, CO-CH.Cl); 2.1 (s, 3H, CH₃-Ar); 2.4 (s, 3H, -COCH₃-Ar) (ppm).

Biological activity:

The screening for cardiovascular activity was done on chloralose (80 mg/kg) anaesthetized dogs*. The ALD₅₀ values were determined in albino mice*.

Eleven compounds (IVb, IVd, IVe, IVf, IVg, IVh, IVi, Va, Vd, Vh and Vi) showed transient, mild to moderate hypotension lasting for less than 5 min. The rest of the compounds were devoid of activity.

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Synthesis of Some N¹-(2'-Alkyl or Aryl-6',8'-Substituted Quinazolone-3'-yl Aminoacetyl)-N⁸-Aryl Ureas and Their *in vivo* Action on Caecal Amoebiasis of Rats

V. S. MISRA, V. K. SAXENA and RASHMI SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow,
Lucknow-226 007

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VARIOUS quinazolones have been shown to exhibit appreciable *in vitro* amoebicidal activity against *E. histolytica*¹⁻³. Recently, a new pharmaceutical preparation containing a urea moiety has been claimed as a good *in vitro* amoebicide against *S. russeli*⁴. Moreover, the amoebicidal activity of the compound containing a CONH-COCH₂ group (in haloacetomides) has long been known⁵⁻⁶. Based on these considerations twenty four new N¹-(2'-alkyl or aryl-6',8'-substituted quinazolone-3'-yl amino acetyl)-N⁸-aryl ureas have been synthesised with a view to enhance the antiamoebic activity through the introduction of quinazolone moiety in aryl ureas. The results of these studies are presented in this communication.

Experimental

The title compounds were synthesised according to the route shown below.

N¹- α -Chloroacetyl-N⁸-aryl ureas⁷, 2-aryl-6,8-substituted benzoxazinones⁸ and 2-alkyl-6,8-substituted benzoxazinones⁹ were prepared by reported methods. Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

2-Alkyl/aryl-3-amino-6,8-substituted quinazolones: To the 2-alkyl/aryl-6,8-substituted benzoxazinone (0.01 mole), hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mole) was added and the mixture heated under reflux for 1 hr at 120-125°. The white fluffy mass obtained on cooling was recrystallised from methanol. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

N¹-(2'-Alkyl/aryl-6',8'-substituted quinazolone-3'-yl amino acetyl) N⁸-aryl ureas: A mixture of 2-alkyl/aryl-3-amino-6,8-substituted quinazolone (0.001 mole), N¹- α -chloro acetyl-N⁸-aryl ureas (0.001 mole) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.0015 mole) in anhydrous acetone (15 ml) was refluxed on a water bath under anhydrous conditions for 7-8 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the excess acetone distilled off. The solid so obtained was treated with boiling methanol and filtered immediately. The filtrate was concentrated and cooled for obtaining a solid product. The title compounds thus obtained after cooling were filtered and recrystallised from methanol (Table 2). The structure of the compounds was confirmed by the presence of characteristic ir spectral bands at 1720-1700 (C=O of amide), 3200-3100 (-NH-), 1680-1660 O=C of quinazolone) and 1600 (C=N) cm⁻¹.

Amoebicidal activity: *E. histolytica* (strain B-1) isolated from an acute case of human amoebiasis was used for the production of experimental caecal amoebiasis of rats. The amoebae were obtained in culture according to the method of Das and Singh in modified Boeck and Drbholav's medium with *Erchemichia coli* as a predominant bacterial associate.

Twenty one day old albino rats (Drackray strain) were used for these studies. The rats were prepared for infection by feeding them for 7 days on an autoclaved rice diet which has been found to produce consistent results in the production of caecal amoebiasis of rats.

The rats were inoculated with 0.2 ml of amoebic inoculum containing about 100,000 trophozoites of *E. histolytica* directly into the caecum by laparotomy (under ether anaesthesia) and the incision caused by suture. Infected rats were treated with the test compounds at a dose of 100 mg/kg orally once daily for five successive days.

The treated rats alongwith the untreated controls were scarified a day after the test administration and the presence or absence of amoebae in the caecal contents and in the mucosal scrapping determined through microscopic examination and culture methods and the gradation of infection determined.

Result

The results presented in Table 3 show the *in vivo* efficacy of compounds no. 3,7,17 and 22 (Table 2) on experimental caecal amoebiasis of rats. None of the test compounds exerted *in vivo* amoebicidal action on the trophozoite of *E. histolytica* in the